

IMPACT AREAS OF DIGITAL CULTURAL PARTICIPATION LITERATURE REVIEW

In this document you can find a wide literature review on the importance of cultural active participation in the digital sphere, and some concrete and illustrative examples per each one of the areas that pertain to the Change Impact Assessment Framework

1. Innovation and knowledge

- Co-creation and bottom-up capacity building
- Measure of improvement of skills and knowledge

Examples and best cases

- Michelangelo foundation and the Homo Faber platform (<https://www.homofaber.com/en/guide>)
- Co-creative practices on tiktok became a research topic for artists (<https://www.qgazette.com/articles/infinite-duets-co-creating-on-tiktok/>)
- Better Together An Inquiry into Collective Art Practice, STUDIO (2007). The STUDIO is committed to supporting and advocating collective art practice (<https://drive.google.com/file/d/112dsx2k7qVFin5caPOrk6aTxcQBNJk26/view?usp=sharing>)

References

- Baioni, M., Ceschel, F., Demartini, P., Marchegiani, L., Marchiori, M., & Marucci, F. (2021). Spread the Voice! Digital Social Platforms as Conveyors of Innovation of Cultural Heritage in Europe. *Sustainability*, 13(22), 12455.
- Bakhshi, H., McVittie, E., & Simmie, J. (2008). *Creating Innovation: Do the creative industries support innovation in the wider economy?* (pp. 1-40). London: Nesta.
- Carlsson, B., Jacobsson, S., Holmén, M., & Rickne, A. (2002). Innovation systems: analytical and methodological issues. *Research policy*, 31(2), 233-245.
- Gruenfeld, E. (2010). Thinking creatively is thinking critically. *New directions for youth development*, 2010(125), 71-83.
- Mačiulienė, M., & Skaržauskienė, A. (2016). Emergence of collective intelligence in online communities. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(5), 1718-1724.
- Muthukrishna, M., & Henrich, J. (2016). Innovation in the collective brain. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 371(1690), 20150192.
- Schimmelpfennig, R., Razek, L., Schnell, E., & Muthukrishna, M. (2022). Paradox of diversity in the collective brain. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*, 377(1843), 20200316.
- Tremblay, D. G., & Pilati, T. (2013). Social innovation through arts and creativity. *The international handbook on social innovation: Collective action, social learning and transdisciplinary research*, 67-79.
- Turşie, C. Participatory Practices in European Capitals of Culture. In *Innovative Instruments for Community Development in Communication and Education* (pp. 195-211). Trivent Publishing.

2. Welfare and well-being

- Personal and collective psycho-physical benefits
- Measure of improvement of well-being

Examples and best cases

- Museum uses Virtual Reality to allow blind people to 'see' famous sculptures (<https://www.museumnext.com/article/museum-uses-virtual-reality-to-allow-blind-people-to-see-famous-sculptures/>)
- Fondazione Medicina a Misura di Donna Onlus, medical humanities and cultural welfare (<http://www.ilgiornaledellefondazioni.com/content/una-sistematica-alleanza-tra-cultura-e-salute-la-cura-delle-pazienti-al-sant%E2%80%99anna-di-torino>)
- Cultural active participation in ECoC 2019 generated psychological wellbeing in participants (<https://www.matera-basilicata2019.it/it/report-2019/studi-valutativi-su-matera-2019/co-creare-matera.html>)
- Statens Museum for Kunst: The social impact of using art to increase civic participation of young people (<https://pro.europeana.eu/post/statens-museum-for-kunst-the-social-impact-of-using-art-to-increase-civic-participation-of-young-people-2018>)

References

- Ascolani, F., Cacovean, C., Passaretti, A., Portaluri, T., Sacco, P. L., Uboldi, S., & Zbranca, R. (2020). Art consumption and well-being during the Covid-19 pandemic.
- Billington, J., Davis, P., & Farrington, G. (2013). Reading as participatory art: An alternative mental health therapy. *Journal of Arts & Communities*, 5(1), 25-40.
- Cheung, M. C., Law, D., Yip, J., & Wong, C. W. (2019). Emotional responses to visual art and commercial stimuli: implications for creativity and aesthetics. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 14.
- Grossi, E., Sacco, P. L., Blessi, G. T., & Cerutti, R. (2011). The impact of culture on

the individual subjective well-being of the Italian population: An exploratory study. *Applied research in quality of life*, 6(4), 387-410.

- Grossi, E., Tavano Blessi, G., Sacco, P. L., & Buscema, M. (2012). The interaction between culture, health and psychological well-being: Data mining from the Italian culture and well-being project. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 13(1), 129-148.
- Johansson, V., Islind, A. S., Lindroth, T., Angenete, E., & Gellerstedt, M. (2021). Online communities as a driver for patient empowerment: Systematic review. *Journal of medical Internet research*, 23(2), e19910.
- Konlaan, B. B., Bygren, L. O., & Johansson, S. E. (2000). Visiting the cinema, concerts, museums or art exhibitions as determinants of survival: a Swedish fourteen-year cohort follow-up. *Scandinavian journal of public health*, 28(3), 174-178.
- Pauwels, E. K., Volterrani, D., Mariani, G., & Kostkiewics, M. (2014). Mozart, music and medicine. *Medical Principles and Practice*, 23(5), 403-412.
- Turner, R., & Whitehead, C. (2008). How collective representations can change the structure of the brain. *Journal of Consciousness Studies*, 15(10-11), 43-57.

3. Sustainability and environment

- Awareness and tools for action
- Measure of improvement of awareness and knowledge

Examples and best cases

- Open access collection of digitized artworks about Climate Change. Close to 1500 artists from 95 countries, visual works on climate change, with a focus on hope and solutions. All the works in The Climate Collection are free to use and adapt non commercially to anyone, anywhere in the world, communicating on climate. (<https://artistsforclimate.org/>)
- Digital book club about Climate Change: The Brooklyn Public Library and advocacy group Writers Rebel NYC have launched Climate Reads, a yearlong, online book club and discussion series open to readers anywhere in the world (<https://hyperallergic.com/589738/climate-reads-book-club-brooklyn-public-library/>)

References

- Bernárdez Rodal, A., Padilla Castillo, G., & Sosa Sánchez, R. P. (2019). From Action Art to Artivism on Instagram: Relocation and instantaneity for a new geography of protest. *Catalan journal of communication & cultural studies*, 11(1), 23-37.
- Crociata, A., Agovino, M., & Sacco, P. L. (2015). Recycling waste: Does culture matter?. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics*, 55, 40-47.
- Hautea, S., Parks, P., Takahashi, B., & Zeng, J. (2021). Showing they care (or don't): Affective publics and ambivalent climate activism on TikTok. *Social Media+ Society*, 7(2), 20563051211012344.
- Lehbrink, M. (2020). *Being green on Instagram: A qualitative study on how green influencers are composing their messages and arguments of sustainability in their Instagram posts* (Bachelor's thesis, University of Twente).
- Roosen, L. J., Klöckner, C. A., & Swim, J. K. (2018). Visual art as a way to communicate climate change: a psychological perspective on climate change-related art. *World Art*, 8(1), 85-110.
- Russo, A., & Perrini, F. (2010). Investigating stakeholder theory and social capital:

CSR in large firms and SMEs. *Journal of Business ethics*, 91(2), 207-221.

- Schmidt, L., Nave, J. G., & Guerra, J. (2006). Who's afraid of Local Agenda 21? Top-down and bottom-up perspectives on local sustainability. *International Journal of Environment and Sustainable Development*, 5(2), 181-198.
- Sommer, L. K., & Klöckner, C. A. (2021). Does activist art have the capacity to raise awareness in audiences?—A study on climate change art at the ArtCOP21 event in Paris. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 15(1), 60.
- Stanley, P. (2020). Unlikely hikers? Activism, Instagram, and the queer mobilities of fat hikers, women hiking alone, and hikers of colour. *Mobilities*, 15(2), 241-256.

4. Social cohesion

- Intersectional community building and intercultural dialogue
- Measure of improvement of social skills and overcoming social barriers

Examples and best cases

- Social Street is a form of neighborhood communities managed collectively online and implemented offline, whose purpose is to «promote socialization between neighbors in the same street in order to build relationships, to interchange needs, to share expertise and knowledges, to implement common interest projects, with common benefits from a closer social interaction [...] It is a no-profit activity with social purpose. Social Street is not pursuing any political, religious, ideological view. It brings people together with the sole criterion of the proximity between area residents. (<http://www.socialstreet.it/>)
- Best practice of participative street art project where local citizens are involved in the decisional phases in order to collectively reason around their district's identity. (<https://orticamemoria.com/>)
- Citizen Art and Human Rights: Collective Theatre Creation as a Way of Combating Exclusion. (<https://www.tate.org.uk/art/art-terms/p/participatory-art>)
- The impact on co-creative and participatory projects on the city of Matera in 2019. (https://www.matera-basilicata2019.it/images/valutazioni/Co_creatore_a_Matera_web.pdf)
- Digital clothes industry - a co-creation process. (<https://dressx.com/>)

References

- Anderson, E., Walker, J., Kafai, Y. B., & Lui, D. (2017, August). The gender and race of pixels: an exploration of intersectional identity representation and construction within minecraft and its community. In *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on the Foundations of Digital Games* (pp. 1-10).
- Amin, A. (2002). Ethnicity and the multicultural city: living with diversity. *Environment and planning A*, 34(6), 959-980

- Buendía, F. C. (2010). More carrots than sticks: Antanas Mockus's civic culture policy in Bogotá. *New directions for youth development*, 2010(125), 19-32.
- Deindl, C., Brandt, M., & Hank, K. (2016). Social networks, social cohesion, and later-life health. *Social Indicators Research*, 126(3), 1175-1187.
- Hamilton, W. L., Zhang, J., Danescu-Niculescu-Mizil, C., Jurafsky, D., & Leskovec, J. (2017, May). Loyalty in online communities. In *Eleventh international AAAI conference on web and social media*.
- Hollinger, D. M. (2006). *Instrument of social reform: A case study of the Venezuelan system of youth orchestras*. ProQuest.
- Jeannotte, M. S. (2003). Singing alone? The contribution of cultural capital to social cohesion and sustainable communities. *The International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 9(1), 35-49.
- Lazzeretti, L. (2022). What is the role of culture facing the digital revolution challenge? Some reflections for a research agenda. *European Planning Studies*, 30(9), 1617-1637.
- Madon, S., Jussim, L., Keiper, S., Eccles, J., Smith, A., & Palumbo, P. (1998). The accuracy and power of sex, social class, and ethnic stereotypes: A naturalistic study in person perception. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 24(12), 1304-1318.
- McCraty, R. (2017). New frontiers in heart rate variability and social coherence research: techniques, technologies, and implications for improving group dynamics and outcomes. *Frontiers in public health*, 5, 267.
- Miño-Puigcercós, R., Rivera-Vargas, P., & Cobo Romani, C. (2019). Virtual communities as safe spaces created by young feminists: Identity, mobility and sense of belonging. In *Identities, youth and belonging* (pp. 123-140). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Muñoz-Bellerín, M., & Cordero-Ramos, N. (2021). Citizen art and human rights: Collective theater creation as a way of combating exclusion. *Social Inclusion*, 9(4), 106-115.
- Roy, S., & Kundu, D. V. (2017). Promoting youth participation for peace and intercultural dialogue through new media and digital literacy. *Research Expo*

International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, VII, 48-55.

- Tartari, M., Pedrini, S., & Sacco, P. L. (2022). Urban 'beautification and its discontents: the erosion of urban commons in Milan. *European Planning Studies*, 30(4), 643-662.
- Thambu, N., & Rahman, M. H. A. (2017). Forum Theatre as a behavior change strategy: Qualitative findings from Moral Education class. *SEARCH: The Journal of the South East Asia Research Centre for Communications and Humanities*, 9(1), 25-46.
- Tombleson, B., & Wolf, K. (2017). Rethinking the circuit of culture: How participatory culture has transformed cross-cultural communication. *Public Relations Review*, 43(1), 14-25.
- Valdesolo, P., Ouyang, J., & DeSteno, D. (2010). The rhythm of joint action: Synchrony promotes cooperative ability. *Journal of experimental social psychology*, 46(4), 693-695.
- Washington, D. M., & Beecher, D. G. (2010). Music as social medicine: Two perspectives on the West-Eastern Divan Orchestra. *New directions for youth development*, 2010(125), 127-140.

5. New forms of entrepreneurship

- Crossover business models between emerging technologies and culture
- Measure of innovation level

Examples and best cases

- Artists and arts organizations joined the Discord platform, initially populated by gamers, in order to capitalize on Discord's potential for creation and play and for community building.
(<https://hyperallergic.com/632565/how-artists-used-the-discord-app-to-build-community-during-covid-19/>)
- Creation of new jobs related to digital platforms such as Tiktok and Instagram (GIF creator, makeup artist for Instagram reels, ...).
- League of their own is an art and lifestyle collective that seeks to educate and encourage young collectors and creators—live with these pieces and use their social media channels to share their collections with others.
(<https://www.artsy.net/article/artsy-editorial-collective-instagram-youtube-demystify-art-collecting>)
- How artists used the discord app to build community during COVID-19. As more artists and arts organizations join the platform initially populated by gamers, they have capitalized on Discord's potential for creation and play (crossover target/platform).
(<https://hyperallergic.com/632565/how-artists-used-the-discord-app-to-build-community-during-covid-19/>)
- Museums/CHis Apps that create a digital visitors experience in different ways:
 1. SMARTIFY: the world's most downloaded museum app for remixing images, a dedicated space for inspiration and discovery that connects collections and audiences.
 2. Muselfie from The National Museum in Warsaw's collection;
 3. VanGo Yourself: an online site that allows to recreate classic scenes from the world's most famous painter Van Gogh and then share it with friends
 4. One Minute: an app that uses image recognition to identify artworks and offer visitors short, bite-size reflections about them. It makes use of the digital heritage of the museum by connecting with the real-life visitor taking tours of the museum, offering short reflections and information about the

artworks.

References

- Dowling, D., Rose, S., & O'Shea, E. (2015). Reconsidering Humanities Programmes in Australian Universities: Embedding a New Approach to Strengthen the Employability of Humanities Graduates by Empowering Them as 'Global Citizens'. *Social Alternatives*, 34(2), 52-62.
- Eikhof, D. R., & Haunschild, A. (2006). Lifestyle meets market: Bohemian entrepreneurs in creative industries. *Creativity and innovation management*, 15(3), 234-241.
- Garlandini, A. (2021). Museums and Heritage in the digital age. The challenge of cultural change and technological innovation. *SCIRES-IT-SCientific RESearch and Information Technology*, 11(1), 11-18.
- Hisrich, R. D., & Soltanifar, M. (2021). Unleashing the creativity of entrepreneurs with digital technologies. In *Digital Entrepreneurship* (pp. 23-49). Springer, Cham.
- Literat, I. (2012). The work of art in the age of mediated participation: Crowdsourced art and collective creativity. *International journal of communication*, 6, 23.
- Mason, M. (2008). *The Pirate's Dilemma, How Youth Culture is Reinventing Capitalism*, 1-st ed.
- Ross, F. (2020). Co-creation via digital fashion technology in new business models for premium product innovation: Case-studies in menswear and womenswear adaptation. In *Sustainable business: Concepts, methodologies, tools, and applications* (pp. 1147-1172). IGI Global.
- Scott, A. J. (2006). Entrepreneurship, innovation and industrial development: geography and the creative field revisited. *Small business economics*, 26(1), 1-24.

6. Learning society

- From school to lifelong learning
- Measurement of new specific knowledge acquisition regardless the age phase

Examples and best cases

- Fondation Hermes and Manufacto project.
(<https://www.fondationentreprisehermes.org/en/project/manufacto-2020-2021>)
(<https://www.artscouncil.org.uk/blog/how-adapt-participatory-arts-activities-lockdown-good-practices-during-lockdown>)
- Homo Faber is a digital platform of fine craftsmanship in Europe, that allows intergenerational sharing of knowledge. The Guide features the talented artisans who have exhibited in Venice at Homo Faber: Crafting a more human future and many more, as well as ateliers, manufacturers, museums and experiences. Connect with the continent's crafting excellence, organize to meet artisans, participate in masterclasses or guided tours of workshops, find unique handcrafted objects, and be inspired by the creativity that lies just around the corner.
(<https://www.homofaber.com/en/guide>)
- Arts and Culture Google is a non-profit initiative. In collaboration with cultural institutions and artists around the world their mission is to preserve and bring the world's art and culture online so it's accessible to anyone, anywhere.
(<https://artsandculture.google.com/>)

References

- Alexenberg, Mel, and Miriam Benjamin. "Creating public art through intergenerational collaboration." *Art Education* 57.5 (2004): 13-18.
- Burke, G., Alfrey, L., Hall, C., & O'Connor, J. (2021). Drawing with Art-Well-Being: Intergenerational Co-Creation with Seniors, Children and the Living Museum. *International Journal of Art & Design Education*, 40(3), 630-654.
- Chiong, C. (2009, July). Can video games promote intergenerational play & literacy learning? In *Report from a research & Design Workshop* (pp. 8-12).
- DiMaggio, P. (1982). Cultural capital and school success: The impact of status culture participation on the grades of US high school students. *American*

sociological review, 189-201.

- Hawkey, R. (2004). *Learning with digital technologies in museums, science centers and galleries* (Vol. 9). Bristol, UK: Nesta Futurelab.
- Herrmann, E., Call, J., Hernández-Lloreda, M. V., Hare, B., & Tomasello, M. (2007). Humans have evolved specialized skills of social cognition: The cultural intelligence hypothesis. *science*, 317(5843), 1360-1366.
- Lankester, A., Hughes, H., & Foth, M. (2018). Mapping a connected learning ecology to foster digital participation in regional communities. In *Digital Participation through Social Living Labs* (pp. 141-171). Chandos Publishing.
- Phillips, L. G., & Tossa, W. (2017). Intergenerational and intercultural civic learning through storied child-led walks of Chiang Mai. *Geographical Research*, 55(1), 18-28.
- Sternberg, R. J. (1997). The concept of intelligence and its role in lifelong learning and success. *American psychologist*, 52(10), 1030.
- Zhang, F., & Kaufman, D. (2016). A review of intergenerational play for facilitating interactions and learning. *Gerontechnology*, 14(3), 127-138.

7. Collective identity

- Digital Heritage Communities
- Measurement of levels of gathering of a group around a cultural asset and of its maintenance and sustainment

Examples and best cases

- Accidentally Wes Anderson. (<https://www.instagram.com/accidentallywesanderson/> and <https://www.bbc.com/culture/article/20201123-accidentally-wes-anderson-when-real-life-meets-film-fantasy>;
https://st.ilssole24ore.com/art/cultura/2014-02-22/il-soft-power-wes-anderson-201904.shtml?uuid=ABv6iTy&refresh_ce=1)
- CHIs can be the physical venue for hosting online heritage communities such as the Cosplayers' ones, who are created and fed by a DCH asset like Animes. (<https://fanboyfactor.com/2017/05/museum-hosts-cosplay/>)
- Online communities and their impact on artists. (<https://art.art/blog/online-communities-are-the-future-for-artists-heres-why>)
- Europeana Communities call themselves "Digital Heritage Communities". (<https://pro.europeana.eu/europeana-network-association/communities>)

References

- Burkey, B. (2022). From Bricks to Clicks: How Digital Heritage Initiatives Create a New Ecosystem for Cultural Heritage and Collective Remembering. *Journal of Communication Inquiry*, 46(2), 185-205.
- Boffone, T., & Jerasa, S. (2021). Toward a (Queer) Reading Community: BookTok, Teen Readers, and the Rise of TikTok Literacies. *Talking Points*, 33(1), 10-16.
- Esposito, L., Piga, E., Ruggiero, A., & Ragone, G. (2014). Technology, Imagination, Narrative Forms. *Technology*, 4(8).
- Feng, X. (2020). <? covid19?> Curating and Exhibiting for the Pandemic: Participatory Virtual Art Practices During the COVID-19 Outbreak in China. *Social Media+ Society*, 6(3), 2056305120948232.

- Heger, A. K., & Gaertner, L. (2018). Testing the identity synergy principle: Identity fusion promotes self and group sacrifice. *Self and Identity*, 17(5), 487-499.
- Hill, N. L. (2017). Embodying cosplay: Fandom communities in the USA.
- Hoff, E. (2017). Digital Cosplay and Postmodern Constructs of Community. *The Phoenix Papers-A journal of fandom and neomedia studies (FANS)*, Plano, 3(1).
- Karpati, A., Freedman, K., Castro, J. C., Kallio-Tavin, M., & Heijnen, E. (2017). Collaboration in visual culture learning communities: Towards a synergy of individual and collective creative practice. *International Journal of Art & Design Education*, 36(2), 164-175.
- Marlowe, J. M., Bartley, A., & Collins, F. (2017). Digital belongings: The intersections of social cohesion, connectivity and digital media. *Ethnicities*, 17(1), 85-102.
- Mutibwa, D. H., Hess, A., & Jackson, T. (2020). Strokes of serendipity: Community co-curation and engagement with digital heritage. *Convergence*, 26(1), 157-177.
- Russo, A., Watkins, J., Kelly, L., & Chan, S. (2008). Participatory communication with social media. *Curator: The Museum Journal*, 51(1), 21-31.
- Vries, G. D. (2019). Cultural Freedom in European Foreign Policy.

8. Soft power

- Power to the people
- Measure of the influence of cultural and imagological power on actions and behaviors

Examples and best cases

- Diet Prada, a digital community strongly influencing the fashion world. (<https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/intellect/cc/2019/00000006/00000001/art00006>)
- South Korean pop culture. (<https://mochi.dance>)

References

- Feng, X. (2020). Curating and Exhibiting for the Pandemic: Participatory Virtual Art Practices During the COVID-19 Outbreak in China. *Social Media+ Society*, 6(3), 2056305120948232.
- Gerrie, V. (2019). The Diet Prada effect: 'Call-out culture in the contemporary fashionscape. *Clothing Cultures*, 6(1), 97-113.
- Haneş, N., & Andrei, A. (2015, November). Culture as soft power in international relations. In *International Conference Knowledge-Based Organization* (Vol. 21, No. 1, pp. 32-37).
- Jaramillo-Dent, D., Contreras-Pulido, P., & Pérez-Rodríguez, A. (2022). Immigrant Influencers on TikTok: Diverse Microcelebrity Profiles and Algorithmic (In) Visibility. *Media and Communication*, 10(1), 208.
- Jaffe, E. D., & Nebenzahl, I. D. (2006). *National image & competitive advantage: The theory and practice of place branding*. Copenhagen Business School Press.
- Kim, Y. (2022). Soft Power and Cultural Nationalism: Globalization of the Korean Wave. In *Media in Asia* (pp. 93-106). Routledge.
- McClory, J. (2010). The new persuaders. *Institute for Government/Monocle*.
- Nye Jr, J. S. (2004). *Soft power: The means to success in world politics*. Public affairs.
- Tomka, G. (2013). Reconceptualizing cultural participation in Europe: Grey literature

review. *Cultural trends*, 22(3-4), 259-264.